

STUDIES ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL ACTIVITY OF MIXTURES OF VANADIC ACID AND TARTARIC ACID.
PART II. PHOTOCATALYSIS BY COLLOIDAL MICELLE OBTAINED BY THE REDUCTION OF VANADIC ACID AND TARTARIC ACID: INDUCED OPTICAL ACTIVITY BY CIRCULARLY POLARISED LIGHT.

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The influence of *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light on the photocatalytic oxidation of tartaric acid by persulphate using as photocatalytic agent circularly dichroic micelles, obtained by the reduction of vanadic acid and *d*- or *l*-tartaric acid, has been studied, and differences obtained for the velocity of the reaction in *d*- and *l*-light. Dextro- and laevo-rotations have been induced by the action of circularly polarised light on the photo-oxidation of racemic acid by persulphate using as photocatalytic agent the colloidal micelle obtained by the reduction of vanadic acid and racemic acid.

Cotton (*J. chim. phys.*, 1909, 7, 87; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 377) was the first to indicate that success in the field of 'Asymmetric Synthesis', might be achieved by making use of substances which exhibit circular dichroism. Modern theories of photochemical reactions postulate that the amount of photochemical transformation is proportional to the number of light quanta absorbed by the reacting molecules. If a racemic compound is illuminated by *d*-circularly polarised light, and the circular dichroism exhibited is such that the *d*-variety absorbs more of *d*-light than the *l*-variety, then it is to be expected that the rate of transformation of the *d*-variety will be faster than that of the *l*-variety. The result will be that, as photodecomposition proceeds in *d*-light, the inactive racemic mixture will develop increasing laevo-rotation. The essential conditions for success are, however, the following :

(i) The radiations used for photochemical transformation should correspond with the absorption band which is characteristic of the asymmetric electronic banding as indicated by Drude's equation for rotatory dispersion,

$$a = \sum \frac{k_m}{\lambda^3 - \lambda_m^2}$$

where a = observed rotation at wave-length λ , λ_m = wave-length corresponding to the characteristic frequency of vibration, and k_m = constant.

(ii) The substance should exhibit circular dichroism in the neighbourhood of the band head.

After Cotton's unsuccessful experiments (*loc. cit.*) several workers carried out photochemical reactions in circularly polarised light, as well as by passing plane-polarised light through a magnetic field parallel to its lines of force (Curie, *J. Physique*, 1894, 3, 409); they did not get positive results. Kuhn and Braun (*Naturwiss.*, 1927, 17, 227) were the first to demonstrate the asymmetric photodecomposition of an externally compensated compound. They observed a small rotation in the photolysis of alcoholic solutions of racemic-ethyl- α -bromopropionate in circularly polarised light. Kuhn and Knopf (*Naturwiss.*, 1930, 18, 183; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, B7, 292) exposed to circularly polarised light hexane solutions of the racemic form of α -azidopropionic dimethylamide and obtained rotations of the order of a degree. Mitchell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1829) observed appreciable rotations on exposing the inactive humulene nitrosite to circularly polarised light. Karagunis and Drikos (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, B26, 428) obtained rotations of the order of 0.08° in the chlorination of the phenyl-biphenyl- α -naphthyl methyl radical in *d*- and *l*-light.

The well known experiments of Weigert (*Ann. Physik*, 1920, 36, 681; *Naturwiss.*, 1928, 16, 163) and Zocher and Copper (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 132, 303, 313) on the anisotropy of thin layers of silver halide, irradiated with polarised light, promise interesting developments. Bredig *et al* (*Biochem. Z.*, 1912, 46, 7; 1932, 250, 414) have demonstrated the parallelism between selective enzyme action and that of simple optically active catalysts.

In the present investigation, the influence of circularly polarised light on the photo-oxidation of tartaric acid by persulphate using photocatalytic colloidal systems, obtained by the reduction of vanadic acid and *d*-, *l*-, *dl*-, and racemic acids, has been studied.

Photocatalysis.

The red solution obtained by the addition of sodium metavanadate to *d*-, *l*- or racemic-tartaric acid does not exhibit circular dichroism in the visible region. On the other hand, if a mixture (at p_H less than 4) of *d*- or *l*-tartaric acid and sodium vanadate containing an excess of tartaric acid is exposed to light until the whole of the vanadium in the sol is reduced from the polyvanadic (V^5) to the polyvanadous (V^4) stage (Rama Char, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 507) $V_2O_5 \rightarrow V_2O_4$, a violet or blue coloured colloidal solution is obtained which is both circularly dichroic and optically active.

This solution contains free tartaric acid and is quite stable up to p_n 3.3 for several days. The reduced sol obtained from racemic or *dl*-tartaric acid (mixture of *d*- and *l*- acids in equimolar proportions) is neither dichroic nor optically active.

It is well known that vanadyl compounds are powerful reducing agents. They also act as catalysts in some reactions, *e.g.*, reduction of chloric acid by hydrogen iodide, the catalytic action depending on an oscillation between the two oxides, V_2O_4 and V_2O_5 . The reduced vanadium micelle (*i.e.* reduced tartaric acid-vanadate colloidal micelle containing vanadium in the polyvanadous state) reduces hydrogen peroxide, potassium chlorate, persulphate, permanganate, bromine etc. ; it is oxidised back in this process : V^5 (red or yellow) $\rightleftharpoons V^4$ (violet or blue). In all cases the rate of oxidation of V^4 increases with increasing p_n . At low p_n , however, the reduction of persulphate by the reduced micelle (which contains an excess of tartaric acid) is small in the dark, whereas the photochemical reaction proceeds rapidly in visible light, tartaric acid being oxidised in the process. In absence of vanadic acid, solutions of persulphate or their mixtures with tartaric acid do not undergo photochemical change in this region. The photoreduction of persulphate by tartaric acid has been found to be catalysed by the reduced vanadic acid-tartaric acid micelle.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Light from a mercury arc was rendered parallel by means of cylindrical lenses. Plane-polarised light was obtained by interposing in the path of the parallel beam a 'polaroid' supplied by the Polaroid Co. The plane polarised beam was then converted into two circularly polarised beams by means of a Fresnel Rhomb.

Measurement of Circular Dichroism in the Visible Region.

Bruhat (*Ann. physique*, 1915, 3, 232, 417 ; *Rev. Opt.*, 1929, 8, 413 ; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1930, 47, 251) has developed a method for the determination of circular dichroism in the visible based on the principle that the axial relations of an elliptically polarised beam of light are changed on passing through a medium which has different absorption coefficients for *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light. In the present investigation, the circular dichroism in the visible region was measured with an experimental arrangement which is a modification of Bruhat's apparatus. The complete arrangement as well as the method of measurement is described below.

Light from a point-o-lite 8000 c. p. Edison lamp after being rendered parallel by a suitable lens falls on the slit of a monochromator (Franz Schmidt and Haensch). It then passes through a polarimeter which consists of a half-shadow polariser and an analyser. A quarter-wave plate holder of the Bruhat's type was used; it rotates on a tubular bearing and carries a slide pierced with 3 holes, any one of which can be brought into register with the aperture of the bearing. Quarter-wave plates, which were correct for the wave-lengths used, were fitted into the two outer holes of the holder, and the arrangement, completed by the addition of a scale and a suitable rotating device, was mounted behind the polariser. A Baly's tube containing the solution under examination was placed between the quarter-wave plate and the analyser; it was provided with special end-plates having negligible birefringence.

The readings were taken as follows: a suitable half-shadow angle was chosen which was greater than the ellipticity to be measured. For a given value of this angle, the positions of the 'zero' of the analyser and the quarter-wave plate are practically the same for all the radiations. The Baly's tube containing the solution was then placed in position, the quarter-wave plate removed and the rotation reading taken in the usual way. The quarter-wave plate was then put back in position, and the equality of illumination was re-established thus: the quarter-wave plate was first turned in the sense which darkened the more illuminated side, the analyser was then turned in the same sense till the common illumination of both the sides was minimum, and the equality of the illumination was finally re-established by rotating the quarter-wave plate. There is no error in thus obtaining compensation for the rotation, if the quarter-wave plate is exact. The angle through which the quarter-wave plate was turned was finally read on the scale carrying it, and it gave the magnitude of the ellipticity of the solution. The sign of the ellipticity was determined by using Cotton's solutions.

The violet reduced vanadium micelle (*i.e.* colloidal micelle containing vanadium in the polyvanadous state, V^4) was obtained by exposing mixtures of the composition 0.08M-tartaric acid, 0.05M- $NaVO_3$ at p_H 2.8 to mercury arc for about 4 hours. The colloidal solution thus obtained was estimated for pentavalent vanadium (polyvanadic acid) iodometrically to ensure complete reduction. The circular dichroism (as ellipticity) and rotatory dispersion of the *d*- and *l*- reduced vanadium micelles (*i.e.* reduced sols obtained from mixtures of vanadate and *d*- and *l*- tartaric acid respectively) are given below. The rotation readings were correct to $\pm 0.01^\circ$ and the ellipticity readings correct to $\pm 0.02^\circ$.

TABLE I.

d-Reduced micelle.

Conc. of reduced micelle (as vanadium) = 0.025M. $p_n = 3^{\circ}2$.
Temp. = 25°. l = length of solution.

Wave-length.	Length of soln.	Rotation.	Length of soln.	Ellipticity.
6700Å	2 cm.	+ 0.24°	2 cm	- 0.29°
6200	4	+ 0.41	4	- 0.21
5780	4	+ 0.30	4	- 0.10°
5460	4	+ 0.19	4	- 0.12
5200	3	+ 0.22	3	- 0.07
4916	2	+ 0.16	4	- 0.06

TABLE II.

l-Reduced micelle.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Wave-length.	Length of soln.	Rotation.	Length of soln.	Ellipticity.
6700 Å	2 cm.	- 0.24°	2 cm.	+ 0.29°
6200	4	- 0.42	4	+ 0.21
5780	4	- 0.29	4	+ 0.09
5460	4	- 0.19	4	+ 0.12
5209	3	- 0.22	3	+ 0.07
4916	2	- 0.16	4	+ 0.06

The results show that the *d*-reduced micelle has a positive rotation and negative ellipticity, whereas the *l*-reduced micelle has the reversed signs for rotation and ellipticity. The magnitude of the rotation as well as the ellipticity is the same for both the micelles in each wave-length. A negative value of ellipticity means that $\epsilon_l - \epsilon_d$ is negative (Mitcheli, "The Cotton Effect and Related Phenomena," 1933) where ϵ_l and ϵ_d are the molecular extinction coefficients in *l*- and *d*-light respectively, i.e., $\epsilon_d > \epsilon_l$, and the anisotropy factor g is negative. The *d*- and *l*-reduced micelles, therefore, have negative and positive values respectively for the anisotropy.

When mixtures of the reduced vanadium micelle and potassium persulphate were exposed to whole visible light (complete range using a 2% KNO_3 filter), it was observed that the initial violet colour did not change even in 8 hours. The mixtures were estimated for V^4 (polyvanadous acid) by microtitration with permanganate. Quick titrations gave satisfactory results in the presence of tartaric acid, and the titration was stopped when the pink colour due to permanganate persisted for 30 seconds. Titrations of the mixtures exposed to strong light for various periods from 4 to 8 hours showed that the concentration of V^4 had not changed. At the same time, iodometric titrations showed that the concentration of persulphate decreased on exposure of the mixtures to light. The titration values (corresponding to 1 c.c. of mixture) for a typical experiment are given below.

TABLE III.

Conc. of reduced vanadium = 0.025 M. Time of exposure = 4 hours
 Conc. of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ = 0.050 M.

	Estimation of V^4 (0.025 N-KMnO ₄)	Estimation of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (0.05 N-thiosulphate.)
Initial	2.0 c.c.	2.0 c.c.
After exposure	2.0	1.3

These observations led to the conclusion that, since there is free tartaric acids in the reduced vanadium micelle, the latter acts as a photocatalyst in the oxidation of tartaric acid by persulphate :

V^5 micelle + tartaric acid + $h\nu \rightarrow \text{V}^4$ micelle + dihydroxytartaric acid, *i.e.* the V^4 (polyvanadous acid) micelle absorbs a quantum of light and reduces persulphate; it is itself oxidised to the V^5 (polyvanadic acid) stage and reduced back to V^4 by tartaric acid, and so on. The photocatalytic cycle, therefore, continues till one of the reactants, *i.e.*, tartaric acid or persulphate is completely transformed.

The photochemical reaction is very large compared with the dark reaction. Table IV gives the effect of the variation of the concentration of the reactants as well as the intensity of the absorbed radiation on the velocity of the photoreduction. dx/dt refers to the number of g. mols transformed per minute (with respect to persulphate), subtracting the dark reaction.

TABLE IV.

Radiation = whole visible. Temp. = 25°. $k = \frac{dx/dt}{I_{\text{abs}} \times \text{conc. of } K_2S_2O_8}$

Conc. of <i>d</i> -reduced micelle.	Conc. of $K_2S_2O_8$.	I_{abs} .	dx/dt .	k .
0.025 <i>M</i> .	0.050 <i>M</i>	8650 ergs	13.3×10^{-6}	3.1×10^{-6}
"	0.025	"	6.5	3.0
"	0.013	"	3.3	3.1
0.013	0.050	5190	8.3	3.2
"	0.025	"	4.6	3.5
"	0.013	"	2.1	3.2
0.025	0.050	8650	13.3	3.1
0.013	"	5190	8.3	3.2
0.006	"	3460	5.4	3.1
0.025	"	8650	13.3	3.1
"	"	4325	6.7	3.1
"	"	2595	4.0	3.1
0.013	"	5190	8.3	3.2
"	"	2595	4.2	3.2

The above results show that the velocity of the reaction is proportional to the intensity of the light absorbed by the reduced micelle and the concentration of persulphate. For the same mixture, it is proportional to I_{abs} . Concordant values are obtained for the constant k . The velocity can, therefore, be expressed in the form

$$dx/dt = 3.1 \times 10^{-6} \times I_{\text{abs}} \times \text{conc. of } K_2S_2O_8.$$

Some reactions were carried out wherein *l*-, *dl*- and racemic-tartaric acids were used for obtaining the reduced vanadium micelle. The results given below show that there is no difference in the velocity of the reaction with these micelles.

TABLE V.

Other conditions same as in Table IV.

Conc. of reduced micelle.	Conc. of $K_2S_2O_8$.	I_{abs} for all micelles.	$dx/dt \times 10^4$			
			<i>d</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>l</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>dl</i> -H ₂ T.	of <i>r</i> -H ₂ T
0.025 <i>M</i>	0.050 <i>M</i>	8650 ergs	13.3	13.5	13.3	13.6
0.013	"	5190	8.3	8.3	8.3	8.5

Temperature Coefficient.—The temperature coefficient (35° - 25°) of this reaction is small, being of the order of 1.05

Reaction in Circularly Polarised Light.

Since the *d*- and *l*-reduced vanadium micelles exhibit circular dichroism in visible light, it might be expected that there will be a difference in the velocity of the reaction in *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light. The experimental results conform to these expectations; they are given below. Permanganate titrations showed that the concentration of reduced vanadium (polyvanadous) did not change during the experiment.

TABLE VI.

Conc. of reduced micelle = 0.025 *M*. Temp. = 25°. $p_n = 3.65$.

Conc. of $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.050$ *M*. Radiation = whole visible.

$I_{abs} = 1384$ ergs in all cases.

Polarised light.	Reduced micelle of				(mean value).
	<i>d</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>l</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>dl</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>r</i> -H ₂ T.	
<i>d</i> -circular	2.71	1.87	2.30	2.30	0.25 to 0.36
<i>l</i> ..	1.87	2.71	2.30	2.30	

TABLE VII.

Conc. of reduced micelle = 0.013 *M*. $p_n = 3.95$. Conc. of $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.050$ *M*.

$I_{abs} = 865$ ergs in all cases. Other conditions same as in Table VI.

Polarised light.	Reduced micelle of			
	<i>d</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>l</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>dl</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>r</i> H ₂ T.
<i>d</i> -circular	1.70	1.17	1.44	1.44
<i>l</i> ..	1.17	1.70	1.44	1.44

The above results show that for the reaction with the *d*-reduced micelle, the velocity in *d*-light is greater than that in *l*-light, the reverse being the case for the *l*-reduced micelle. Also, there is no difference in the velocity in *d*- and *l*-light for the *dl*- or racemic-reduced micelles, the velocity being a mean of the velocities for the *d*- and *l*-micelles taken separately.

These results are in accordance with the dichroism exhibited by these micelles (Tables I and II). The *d*-reduced micelle has a negative anisotropy or $\epsilon_d > \epsilon_l$, i.e., larger fraction of the incident *d*-light is absorbed by the surface layers of the colloidal micelles. Only the radiation that is absorbed on the surface layer of the micelle is capable of bringing about photochemical

transformation, the radiation that penetrates the interior of the colloidal particle being ineffective for photo-reaction. The value of the quantum efficiency shows that about 30% of the total incident light is effective for chemical reaction. In the case of the *d*-reduced micelle, therefore, since $\epsilon_d > \epsilon_l$, the velocity in *d*-light is expected to be greater than that in *l*-light. The *l*-reduced micelle has a positive anisotropy, *i.e.*, $\epsilon_l > \epsilon_d$ and therefore, the velocity in *l*-light is expected to be greater than that in *d*-light. For the *dl*- or racemic-reduced micelles, on the other hand, $\epsilon_d = \epsilon_l$ and there should not be any difference in the velocity of reaction in *d*- and *l*-light. Tables I and II show that the ellipticity of the *d*- and *l*-reduced micelles has a high value (for the same length of solution) in the orange-red region, and that its value is quite large in the yellow, green and blue regions. Experiments performed showed that the photocatalytic reaction takes place in these regions.

Induced Optical Activity.

When racemic- or *dl*-reduced vanadium micelles are used, the velocity of the photoreduction of persulphate is the same in *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light, and is a mean of the velocities with *d*- and *l*-reduced micelles. But the *d*- and *l*-reduced micelles are circularly dichroic. In view of the differential velocity and absorption of the *d*- and *l*-components for the same kind of light (*d*- or *l*-), therefore, it is to be expected that the exposure of mixtures of persulphate and racemic- or *dl*-reduced micelle to *d*- and *l*-light respectively, might result in the development of optical rotation of opposite sign *i.e.*, laevo and dextro respectively. The experimental results given in Table VIII conform to these expectations. The rotation was measured in a Winkel-Zeiss triple-field polarimeter which gave readings correct to $\pm 0.01^\circ$. Permanganate titrations showed that the concentration of the reduced vanadium (polyvanadous) did not change during the exposure.

TABLE VIII.

Length of solution (for rotation readings) = 2.6 cm. Wave-length (for rotation readings) = 5893 Å. Time of exposure = 8 hours.

Other conditions same as in Table VI.

Polarised light.	Observed rotation.		Calc. rotation.
	<i>dl</i> -H ₂ T micelle.	<i>r</i> -H ₂ T micelle.	<i>dl</i> - or <i>r</i> -H ₂ T micelle.
<i>d</i> -circular	-0.06°	-0.06°	-0.06°
	+0.06	+0.06	+0.06

In the above table, the calculated value for the expected rotation is given by

$$\text{Rotation (calc.)} = \mp \frac{\text{Change in rotation on oxidation}}{\text{Change in titre on oxidation}} \times \frac{a-b}{a+b} \times c,$$

for *d*- and *l*- light respectively, where, the ratio (change in rotation/change in titre) is a constant, *a* and *b* are velocities of the photo-reduction (Table VI) with *d*-reduced micelle in *d*- and *l*-light, or with *l*-reduced micelle in *l*- and *d*- light, respectively (the final concentrations being the same as for *r*- or *dl*-reduced micelle), and *c*=change in titre actually observed immediately after the rotation was measured.

Mixtures of persulphate and *d*- or *l*-reduced micelle, were exposed to light for different periods, the rotations were measured and the persulphate estimated. It was found that the ratio (change in rotation/change in titre) is a constant, equal to 4/3.

The experimental results given above show that when the racemic- or *dl*-mixture is exposed to *d*- light, it develops laevo-rotation, and when exposed to *l*- light, it develops dextro-rotation. There is good agreement between the observed and calculated values of the rotation.

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